

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

SERENA Deliverable 1.3 v2

Validation of the maps resulting from the application of the Cookbooks elaborated by WP3, and of EU products elaborated by WP5

Due date of deliverable: M57
Actual submission date: 30.01.2025

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: 1.3 v2

DELIVERABLE TITLE: Validation of the maps resulting from the application of the Cookbooks elaborated by WP3, and of EU products elaborated by WP5

DELIVERABLE TYPE: Report

WORK PACKAGE N: WP1

WORK PACKAGE TITLE: Co-creation and involvement of end-users

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL: PU

ABSTRACT

This report is part of the EJP SOIL SERENA project. It presents the way some stakeholders have been involved in the project to validate mapping products of soil-based ecosystem services and soil threats, at both the national and EU scales.

At national scale, the maps have been produced by some harmonised cookbooks. The cookbooks are first presented and their concern: as far as soil threats are concerned, and as far as soil-based ecosystem services are concerned. A cookbook for an evaluation of bundles is also presented. The list of countries which have evaluated the different products is then precised. The results of the evaluation by stakeholders are commented all together, without any relation to a specific country. They demonstrate that the results are more likely understood by scientists than by policy makers or farmers. For the latter, the scale of the maps are not relevant with their own interest. The maps of erosion, SOC loss and soil sealing seem to be more easily understood by the stakeholder that the GHG regulation, and the bundles, with which stakeholders are not familiar.

At the EU scale, the evaluation has been conducted during a webinar organised by EJP-Soil WP8 (Science to Policy), and only the bundles of either soil threats or soil-based ecosystem services have been evaluated. The stakeholders were usually interested in the approach, acknowledged the results, but the latter sometimes appeared far from the actions they could develop to protect soils.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CC	Climate Change
DG	Directorate-General
DSM	Digital Soil Mapping
DMP	Data Management Plan
EEA	European Environment Agency
ES	Ecosystem Service
ESDAC-JRC	European Soil Data Centre-Joint Research Centre
EU	European Union
LM	Land Management
LU	Land Use
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MS	Member State
NCR	National Communication Representative
RCP	Representative Concentration pathways
SES	Soil Ecosystem Service
SG	Stakeholder Group
ST	Soil Threat
T	Tasks
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

In the SERENA project a specific WP (WP1) has been designed to address end-user participation and engagement at each stage of the project. The objective of this exercise is to involve all relevant actors, from local (e.g. farmers) to regional and national (e.g. ministries) and continental (e.g. administration, EEA, ESDAC-JRC, DG), to understand their needs and expectations and to validate, step by step, the choices made during the project. In addition, relevant actors were invited to evaluate results generated by the project in terms of quality and practical usefulness.

End-users and stakeholders are at the core of the project (Figure 1), so in this way SERENA expects different visions of end-users and stakeholders depending on their own interest, and on the policies to be implemented or to be developed.

The 3 pillars of the SERENA philosophy

Figure 1. The three pillars of SERENA, with Stakeholders at the core of the project. Source: SERENA M6.5.4: 7.

The project has been designed so that stakeholders actively contribute to (Figure 2):

- i) identify the most important STs/SESs to be considered in the project given their specific interest as stakeholders, considering the agro-pedo-climatic context and local, regional, national and EU policies (SERENA deliverable D2.2¹);
- ii) a harmonized terminology by agreeing on definitions and indicators of ST/SES (SERENA deliverable D1.2²)

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10389897>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/13929611>

- iii) co-construct the relevant climate change or land-use, cover, and management change scenarios to be evaluated by SERENA activities (SERENA deliverable D1.4³); and
- iv) validate two final products of SERENA: the maps resulting from the application of the cookbooks produced by WP3 (at national scale) (SERENA deliverable D3.3⁴) and different maps produced by WP5 (at EU scale) (SERENA deliverables D5.1⁵ and D5.2⁶).

Figure 2. The overall goals of the SERENA project. Validation process by stakeholders at the top of the pyramid. Source: SERENA M6.5.4: 6.

2. Involving stakeholders in the SERENA project

2.1. Access to the different categories of stakeholders

Since the beginning of the project, stakeholders have been engaged by SERENA based on the national list established by the EJP SOIL board, and in conjunction with EJP SOIL WP8 (Science to policy interaction) and EJP SOIL WP9 (Dissemination and outreach). Initially there were more than 160 names and related contact information, and other contacts have been added over time, as the database remained open for the entire duration of the project. This database has been compiled by Task 1.1: “Identification, selection and engagement of relevant end-

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/10417014> and <https://zenodo.org/records/13834642>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/13991088>

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/13891492>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/13950477>

users across EJP SOIL countries, and at the European level”, led by TEAGASC and EMU. The stakeholders’ database is securely stored in a TEAGASC server to guarantee Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules. Disclosure of stakeholder data and contacts to project partners follows a strict protocol that takes into account the GDPR. T1.1 leaders provide the stakeholders' contacts only upon request, and all the people accessing the database sign a confidentiality form.

In addition to this national list established by the EJP SOIL board, and depending on the Tasks in which the stakeholders have been asked to collaborate, they have also been contacted through other means, such as i) disseminating questionnaires through social networks; ii) passing out surveys at congresses, specialized workshops or National Soil Hubs meetings; iii) distributing the surveys to scientific societies or farmers' associations, etc. - for instance in T2.2 where the stakeholders helped in defining the most relevant ST and SES for their country. Furthermore, this was the case for the questionnaires given to the stakeholders to answer the questions posed in the joint tasks T1.2-T2.1, to identify the most important STs/SESs to be considered in the SERENA project (<https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13476>); and in the tasks T1.4-T1.2, to co-construct the relevant climate change or land-use, cover and management change scenarios to be evaluated by SERENA activities (<https://zenodo.org/records/13983575>; <https://zenodo.org/records/13983452>; <https://zenodo.org/records/13983195>; <https://zenodo.org/records/13834642>).

2.2. Two methodologies depending on the scale of the products

According to the SERENA proposal, the participation and active collaboration of stakeholders has been also necessary for the **VALIDATION** of certain products developed by WP3 and WP5.

The products to be validated in WP3 are the maps resulting from the application of the different Cookbooks produced within the framework of the SERENA. The method of validation is based on the analyses of a questionnaire sent to the stakeholders in different Member States. Both the method and the results regarding the validation at the national scale are presented in the part 3 of this report.

Regarding WP5, different maps needed also to be validated. The method of validation is based on a webinar with stakeholders where the products were presented and discussed. Both the method and the results regarding the validation at the EU scale are presented in the part 4 of this report.

3. Evaluating the SERENA products at the national scale

3.1. Description of the participatory Design Method

3.1.1. General overview of the method

In order to validate the maps resulting from the application of the Cookbooks produced by WP3, WP1 has worked together with WP3 to establish joint requirements for stakeholders. For this purpose, inter-task meetings have been held, where the actions have been fully defined. A total of 44 scientists from the project partners have participated in the meetings and the subsequent work.

WP1 and WP3 have proposed a participatory process model to validate the results, in line with the recommendations of the European Green Deal, the Mission Board on Soil Health and Food and the Farm to Fork Strategy, which emphasize this process of dialogue with stakeholders involved in soil and water management and policy development.

The purpose is to jointly specify the research design that the working team involved in T3.1 and T3.2 could follow in order to carry out a methodologically sound assessment of “National multi-scale assessments”. Regarding the validation of the products at national level, after several meetings of the working group, it has been decided to design a survey in Google Forms **to evaluate the maps** that have been derived from the Cookbooks for assessing the following indicators of STs, SESs, and bundles:

- **Soil sealing (ST)**
- **Soil erosion (ST) and soil erosion control (SES)**
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation (SES)**
- **SOC loss (ST)**
- **Bundles**

Stakeholders were provided with the maps resulting from cookbook applications, and - where available for their country - also with already existing maps of the ST/SES to be assessed. These previously available maps at national or regional level had already been collected by the SERENA partners in D3.1 (<https://zenodo.org/records/13991088>).

A participatory approach among the SERENA scientists in the different working groups has been adopted to develop the Forms). An intense work has been carried out in order **to design a Form** in which the questions are direct, clear, understandable and open-ended, allowing experts to provide suggestions. The aim of this participatory process is collaborative planning and collective learning, with the ultimate goal of co-creating a document to support Science4Policy, taking into account the stakeholder opinions, collected in the Forms.

It was decided that the Forms would be distributed in the different countries according to the specific characteristics considered by the project members. Different methods were therefore chosen: sending the forms to stakeholders registered in the database provided by T1.1 (on request); selecting a small Focus Group of highly specialized experts at national level; or

sending the forms to colleagues working on the issue at national level, or at regional level in case of regional applications.

3.1.2. Content of the Forms

The forms included different information and questions sections. The structure of the question sections in the forms was the same for each ST, SES or bundle. The Forms differed only in the information sections, because here STs/SESs or bundles were presented. Finally, the Forms were translated into the different languages of the member Countries to facilitate their use by stakeholders. The Forms included the following sections: 1. Preliminary information, 2. Definitions, 3. Presentation of the idea behind the Cookbooks (common methodology, principle), 4. Brief explanation about data and methodologies, and some question sections.

A copy of the different sections is given in the following.

1. Preliminary information:

“EJP SOIL is a European Joint Program on Agricultural Soil Management contributing to key societal challenges including climate change, water and future food security. Its objectives are to develop knowledge, tools and an integrated research community to foster climate-smart sustainable agricultural soil management. In the EJP SOIL framework, SERENA is an internal project, started in November 2021 and lasting for three years. Within SERENA, 24 Partners from 16 EU member states worked together with the final aim to enhance soil policy effectiveness. The main objective of the SERENA project is to assess, analyze and map SES bundles (i.e. the analysis of a set of soil-based ESs, which are repeatedly appearing together in space and time) across European agricultural landscapes, highlighting how soil threats affect the supply of service bundles through adoption of a set of site-specific reference thresholds. The SERENA research approach is based on six main pillars. Among these, two are particularly relevant for this task: 1- SERENA intends to provide STs and soil-based ES evaluation at both the national and European scales, adopting a common methodology (cookbook) to share the indicators to be calculated and the way of evaluating bundles; 2- end-users and stakeholders are at the core of the project: they will collaborate to identify the most important STs/SESs to be considered in the project, to construct the relevant climate change or land-use, cover and management change scenarios, and will evaluate the final products of SERENA.”

2. Definitions:

SOIL THREAT (ST): *Soil threats are processes that could degrade (some of) the functions of soils and the services that soils provide (adapted, after EJP Soil Glossary, online source: <https://ejpsoil.eu/knowledge-sharing-platform/ejp-soil-glossary/>).*

SOIL ECOSYSTEM SERVICES (SES): *Soil Ecosystem Services is the soil-related subset of ecosystem services, directly and quantifiably controlled or provided by soils and their chemical, physical and biological properties, processes and functions (adapted, after Paul et. al., 2021).*

ECOSYSTEM SERVICE / SOIL THREAT BUNDLE: *A set of ecosystem services, soil threats, or the combination of the two, that appear together repeatedly in time or space, as related to a specific context (adapted, after Potschin-Young et. al., 2018, MAES initiative).*

3. Presentation of the idea behind the Cookbooks (common methodology, principle)

“Different STs and SESs are often evaluated in different ways in different parts of Europe, which makes comparison of results from different member states (MS) difficult. The aim of developing cookbooks was to harmonize the methodologies as far as possible, while maintaining enough flexibility to deal with MS-specific conditions. To allow harmonization, the methodologies selected for the cookbooks were a compromise between scientific innovation (to come up with state-of-the-art evaluation) and practical applicability. Applicability allows as many MS as possible to apply the different cookbooks, and required that cookbooks could be applied without being a specialist on specific ST/SES and without the use of specialist equipment or software.”

4. Brief explanation about data and methodologies.

“In the questionnaire, a maximum of 3 maps for each ST or ES are being compared. These 3 maps are:

- *A map made at EU scale using data available at EU level, but clipped here to the extent of the member state (MS)*
- *A map made at national scale prior to SERENA, usually using MS level data*
- *A map made in SERENA by application of the cookbook, using MS level data where available and EU level data where necessary*

Hence, maps differ with respect to the methodology used as well as the data used. It is known that different methodologies can result in different results, and the same is true for data. The use of different input data, even with the same methodology, can also have an influence on results.

The main aim of this questionnaire is to evaluate the results of cookbook application. This is the focus of the first two questions in the questionnaire (on presentation and results). These cookbook results are, if possible, compared to the other maps, but this is not always possible as for some combinations of STs/SESs and MSs not all three kinds of map are available. When this is the case, the third question (on comparison) cannot be, or can only partially be, answered.”

The Forms sent to stakeholders contained then the following questions:

Which member state does the map refer to?							
Questions on the way the results are presented:							
Question	Level of agreement (1: low; 5: very high)						comments, suggestions
	1	2	3	4	5	NA*	
It is easy to understand what the map shows							
The map is useful in the following in one or more areas of application, and I feel comfortable to work with it (fill the record fitting with your expertise)							
- Lighthouse farms							
- Farmers groups							
- National policy stakeholder							
- EU policy maker							
- Scientist							
- Other (please specify)							
The classes used in the legend are appropriate.							

* Don't know/ not applicable

Questions on the results:

If you have expertise on the ST or SES concerned, please fill out the table below as well.

Question	Level of agreement (1: low; 5: very high)						comments, suggestions
	1	2	3	4	5	NA*	
I have expertise for the whole national territory.							
I have local expertise (if so, specify the region).							
The values shown on the map are consistent with my knowledge.							Explain if your response is between 1 and 3.
The spatial patterns shown in the map are consistent with my knowledge.							Explain if your response is between 1 and 3.

* Don't know/ not applicable

Questions on comparison:

If you have expertise on the ST or SES concerned, please fill out the table below as well.

Question	Level of agreement (1: disagree; 3: agree)				Explain your response
	1	2	3	NA*	
The cookbook map is better than the earlier map.					
The cookbook map is better than the EU map.					
The EU map is better than the earlier map					
The best map is: Earlier map / Cookbook map / EU map					

* Don't know/ not applicable

Further comments may be added in the box

3.2. Cookbooks, maps and answers to Forms

3.2.1. Soil Sealing Cookbook

The Cookbook was elaborated by: Daniela Smiraglia, Kasper Cockx, Sabina Asins-Velis, Luca Congedo, Cecilie Foldal, Ines Marinosci, Katrien Oorts, Nicola Riitano, Paolo De Fioravante, Francesca Assennato, Michele Munafò.

To assess the ST “soil sealing” the SERENA project chose the degree of soil sealing as indicator. The degree of soil sealing is the proportion of an area (ha ha^{-1}) that is covered by artificial, (semi-)impermeable materials. Furthermore, to assess the ST soil sealing it is helpful to compare the degree of soil sealing through time ($\text{ha ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

To map and assess the degree of soil sealing at the national level, a hierarchical approach has been proposed:

- Level 1: semi-automatic classification process of multitemporal images. The methodology uses vegetation and backscatter indices calculated over time series of images, and decision rules. The semi-automatic classification supports the subsequent photointerpretation phase based on national orthophotos and other free VHR satellite images (e.g. through Google Earth or Bing services). The final maps are the product of a binary classification (sealed/not sealed) having 10 m spatial resolution;
- Level 2: a more detailed mapping methodology is proposed for supporting users in generating more detailed mapping products, if needed. To monitor the evolution of sealed surfaces a method was developed for automatically generating annual and spatially detailed (1 m resolution) soil sealing maps. These maps combine “known” sealing from administrative databases (buildings and transport infrastructure) with modelled sealing based on a machine learning model.

The Cookbook was applied by: Austria, Belgium (Flanders), Ireland, Italy, Spain and The Netherlands.

Answers were received from: Belgium (Flanders); Ireland; Italy; Spain and The Netherlands

Examples of the maps:

- Italy <https://zenodo.org/records/13951145>;
- Austria <https://zenodo.org/records/13969875>;
- The Netherlands <https://zenodo.org/records/13960888>;

3.2.2. Soil Erosion and Erosion Control Cookbook

The Cookbook was elaborated by: Rudi Hessel, Joao Coblinski, Gabriele Buttafuoco, Sylwia Pindral and Blandine Lemercier, Annamária Laborczi.

To assess soil erosion, the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) was selected because it is conceptually simple and easy to use. RUSLE was designed to calculate the long-term average soil loss from sheet and rill erosion under specific conditions (Renard et al., 1997; Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). In the RUSLE approach, forms of water erosion other than rill and sheet erosion (e.g., gully erosion) or deposition are not considered. The soil loss for a given location is calculated as the product of six factors (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978):

$$A = R \times K \times LS \times C \times P \quad (1)$$

where A ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is the annual average soil loss, R ($\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) is the rainfall-runoff erosivity factor, K ($\text{Mg ha h ha}^{-1} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$) is the soil erodibility factor, LS (dimensionless) is the slope length and slope steepness factor, C (dimensionless, ranges between 0 and 1) is the cover-management factor and P (dimensionless, ranges between 0 and 1) is the support practices factor.

Equation 1 was used for both the ST Soil Erosion and the SES Soil Erosion control. The C-factor (cover-management factor) is used to estimate both the ST and the SES. To estimate the ST soil erosion the C-factor is set to 1, while for the SES soil erosion control a value based on land use, crop type and management is given. The difference with soil erosion is then taken to be the erosion that is prevented by the presence of vegetation.

The Cookbook of Soil Erosion was applied by: Austria, Belgium, Ireland, Lithuania, Spain and The Netherlands. And the Cookbook Erosion+Erosion Control was applied by: France, Hungary, Italy, Poland and Slovakia.

Answers for Soil Erosion were received from: Austria; Ireland; Italy; Spain and The Netherlands; and for Erosion Control from: France; Hungary; Italy; Poland and Slovakia.

Examples of the maps:

- Flanders, Belgium <https://zenodo.org/records/13993235>;
- Ireland <https://zenodo.org/records/13987790>;
- Italy <https://zenodo.org/records/13969798>; <https://zenodo.org/records/13952098>; <https://zenodo.org/records/13951152>;
- The Netherlands <https://zenodo.org/records/13951680>;

3.2.3. Soil Organic Carbon Loss Cookbook

The Cookbook was elaborated by: Gabriele Buttafuoco, Rudi Hessel and Sylwia Pindral.

For the assessment of the SOC loss at the EU Member, the pragmatic indicator “Soil organic carbon (SOC) concentration” was selected (g C kg⁻¹ soil or %, which amounts to g C 100 g⁻¹ soil).

The assessment of the SOC loss indicator at the EU MS level is an extension of SOC concentrations measured at selected sampling points to unsampled locations in each MS. Such an extension requires a spatial analysis of the available SOC data and its prediction to the unsampled locations and its subsequent mapping. The spatial prediction of SOC at unsampled locations might be made using different methods depending on the available data. Among these is the well-known Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) (McBratney et al., 2003), which uses more densely measured auxiliary variables/maps (secondary data, ancillary maps, environmental covariates) to improve soil mapping.

The specific methods to be used within the DSM depend on the availability of data. Useful references can be:

- ✓ Chapter 5 ‘Harmonized procedures for creation of soil maps’. WP6 EJP Soil Deliverable 6.1 ‘Report on harmonized procedures for creation of databases and maps’ (D6.1).
- ✓ SOC mapping Cookbook (<https://www.fao.org/documents/card/en/c/l8895EN/> or WsG folder)

The application of DSM approaches can be facilitated by the DSM workflow developed within EJP Soil WP6 and located in the ISRIC data hub (Genova et al., 2024). Information on how to install and run the DSM workflow can be found at <https://shiny.wur.nl/content/71ff48b3-6e26-4b6b-8d07-ec9a05c64cc8/>. The DSM workflow allows to access a large number of covariate data and scripts to apply different approaches, including algorithms ranging from geostatistics to machine learning.

The Cookbook of SOC Loss was applied by: Belgium, Estonia, France, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Poland and Portugal.

Answers were received from: Estonia; France; Hungary; Ireland; Italy; Lithuania; Poland and Portugal.

Examples of the maps:

- Italy <https://zenodo.org/records/13993045>;
- Estonia <https://zenodo.org/records/13986640>,

3.2.4. Greenhouse gas (GHG) and climate regulation including carbon sequestration Cookbook

The Cookbook was elaborated by: Eduardo Medina-Roldán, Liia Kukk, Sylwia Pindral, and the SERENA GHG Working Group.

As a tool to assess the soil-based ES “greenhouse gas regulation”, the SERENA project developed a methodology (cookbook) using a pragmatic approach (the indicator chosen is not necessarily the best to indicate the ecosystem service in question) based on Net Ecosystem Productivity (NEP).

In this approach, NEP is defined as the difference between gross primary productivity (GPP) and ecosystem respiration (the sum of autotrophic and heterotrophic respiration, Reco). The approach fits GPP and Reco data from Fluxnet stations under wheat (and wheat-mixed; and wheat-other crop rotations) with spatially exhaustive variables of remotely sensed GPP (from MODIS MOD17A2H products), daily soil moisture and monthly temperature. The NEP indicator represents an 8-day value of NEP. Mapping is done using an R script, and/or open-access GIS software and data easily accessible online. The approach is limited to the land cover and operational range of input variable values used to fit the model. Also, the approach is not suitable to produce an annual NEP indicator as the aggregation of individual observations produces error accumulation (this is why a single representative 8-d value for the summer period is provided). Yet, it is practical to map NEP in relatively large areas (regional level for big countries in the EU) using an empirical-based perspective.

The Cookbook of Greenhouse Gas Regulation was applied by: Czechia, Estonia, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Spain and The Netherlands.

Answers were received from: Czechia; Estonia; Ireland; Italy; Poland; Spain and The Netherlands.

Examples of the maps:

- Estonia <https://zenodo.org/records/13959778>;
- Ireland <https://zenodo.org/records/13987916>;
- The Netherlands <https://zenodo.org/records/13960817>;
- Italy <https://zenodo.org/records/13951143>;

3.2.5. Bundles Cookbook

The Cookbook was elaborated by: Eduardo Medina-Roldán, Jessica Reyes Rojas, Nicolas Saby, Joao Coblinski, and the SERENA Bundles Working Group

One of the SERENA key objectives was to produce maps of soil SESs/STs bundles. Bundles are considered as patterns in the spatial and/or temporal association/co-occurrence of such SESs/STs. The SERENA bundles' cookbook used the k-means statistical clustering method to produce such SESs and/or STs bundles. In this way, bundles are essentially clusters of SESs and/or ST's, which multivariate values are closer to each other than to other clusters.

The Cookbook of Bundles was applied by: Czechia, Estonia and Poland.
Answers were received from: Czechia; Estonia and Poland.

Examples of the maps:

- Estonia <https://zenodo.org/records/13951147>

3.3.4. Results of the consultation of some stakeholders

Stakeholders' participation is reflected in the following graphs (Figures 3 and 4). As a whole, 85 replies were collected. The amount of answers from MSs ranges from 21 (Ireland) to 2 (Hungary and Belgium). The distribution of the replies among the cookbooks reflects the number of applications of the cookbook, i.e. 11 (+4), 9, 7, 6, and 4 for Erosion (and erosion control), SOC, GHG, Soil sealing, and bundle, respectively.

Figure 3: Distribution of the replies among the MSs

Figure 4: Distribution of the replies among the cookbooks

The responses provided by the Stakeholders are detailed below. As a whole, the maps based on cookbook seem to fit better to scientific purposes and in little measure to national and EU policy ones, than to farmers ones (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Distribution of the replies to the question about the usefulness of the map, according to the different issues

The weighted mean values showed the highest level of agreement for scientist (3,78) followed respectively by national and EU policy (3,49), lighthouse farms (2,86) and farmers (2,63). In general, the national (or regional) scale of these maps makes their usefulness at farm level quite limited (in this regard, a comment on SOC LOSS map focused on the fact that nationally

modelled data cannot be used at local scales – so not for farmers – because there is no uncertainty in the representation).

Figure 6: Level of agreement for map usefulness according to the different purposes

Comparing the single SES/ST, the previous trend is confirmed (Figure 6). This is particularly true for BUNDLE and SOIL SEALING for whom the level of agreement for scientists' usefulness is 2 points higher than farmers one. Soil sealing has also showed a very high usefulness for policy makers.

The results are in line with the novelty of the adopted methods in some cookbook with respect to other, that can increase the interest of the scientific community. Usefulness of soil sealing for Policy makers is in line with the fact that the adopted method is already used by some MS for policy issue.

Two questions pointed regarding the way the data are presented: “it is easy to understand what the map shows”, and “the classes used in the legend are appropriate” (Figures 7 and 8). There is not a clear trend in the legend evaluation and in the general question on the figure 7. Mean values of agreement ranged from 3,33 of SOC LOSS to 4,25 of soil sealing (Figure 8) for the legend, and from 2,5 for Bundles to 4,4 for soil sealing, for the general question (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Level of agreement for the question "It is easy to understand what the map shows". On the left, mean value of agreement per SES/ST; on the right, distribution of the replies.

Figure 8: Level of agreement for legends adopted in the maps . On the left, mean value of agreement per SES/ST; on the right, distribution of the replies.

The consistency of the maps regarding the knowledge of the stakeholders was evaluated by means of level of agreement with the values and with the pattern (Figure 9). In general, the level of agreement with pattern is slightly higher than with value. In both cases, the best average value of agreement is for soil sealing (4,11 for values; 4,44 for pattern), while a mean degree of agreement was given to erosion (2,88 for values and 2,96 for pattern).

Figure 9: Level of agreement with the values shown in the maps. On the left, mean value of agreement per SES/ST; on the right, distribution of the replies.

Figure 10: Level of agreement with the pattern shown in the maps. On the left, mean value of agreement per SES/ST; on the right, distribution of the replies.

The useful comments by stakeholders may increase the quality and the usefulness of the cookbook and of the maps. For GHG, soil sealing, soil erosion, and SOC LOSS some comments highlighted the limits of legends/scales, which were difficult to interpret. For SOC, an information about the uncertainty is required. Moreover, a comment focused on the difficulty to use national modelled data at the local scale, which is then not appropriate for farmers. For this reason, the only users suggested for being recipients of these maps were extension workers and teachers, for their awareness-raising operations.

For Soil sealing, it was suggested that the map could also be used in a living lab at a regional scale, so that it could be discussed with several different stakeholders involved in the sustainable transformation of that territory.

4. Evaluating the SERENA products at the EU scale

4.1. A participative approach based on a webinar

4.1.1. General overview of the process

To evaluate the SERENA products – maps of soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services at present and in 2050 – some stakeholders involved in actions at the EU scale were invited to a webinar, organised together with EJP SOIL WP8 (Figure 11). Insofar as numerous soil threats have already been published at the EU scale, the webinar was focused on bundles (of soil threats or soil-based ecosystem services). The objective was to receive the stakeholders' feedbacks regarding both the methods developed by the SERENA consortium to map bundles, and to the resulting maps.

Figure 11: Save-the-Date announcement of the SERENA webinar on bundles by EJP SOIL WP8

The products to be evaluated were:

- A **map of bundles of soil threats by 2050 under two contrasted climate scenarios** A **map of bundles of Soil-based ecosystem services for both present and 2050** (by using the same scenarios)

The feedbacks expected from the stakeholders were:

- Do you find these maps **understandable**?
- Do you find these maps **informative**?
- Do you find these maps **of any use for you**?
- How could they **be improved**?

The webinar took place the 24th of January 2025, from 10:00 to 12:00. A general presentation of the methods and products was given by Sophie Cornu. All along the presentation, a Mentimeter session was organised to receive feedbacks.

4.1.2. Quick overview of the products to be evaluated

The EU products of SERENA are extensively described in 2 public deliverables:

- Deliverable 5.1. Maps of soil threat bundles by 2050 (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13891492>)
- Deliverable 5.2. Bundles of soil-based ecosystem services at EU and their evolution by 2050 (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/13950477>)

Scenarios

The use of scenarios was highly important, especially to evaluate soil threats, which are considered in SERENA as processes: a threat can then be described only by comparing two levels of an indicator, here compared between present and 2050.

- ☛ As far as **Land-Use change** is concerned, the LUISA scenarios developed by JRC were used
- ☛ As far as **Climate Change** is concerned, 2 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) scenarios were used: the SSP1-2.6 and the SSP5-8.5

Bundles of soil threats

Four threats were considered for the evaluation of the bundle (Table 1), and each of them was evaluated by modelling.

Table 1: list of the soil threats taken into account in the evaluation of the bundles, together with their indicators

Soil Threat	Indicator
SOC loss	Change in SOC stocks on the whole soil depth (or 1 m) ($\text{kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
Soil Erosion	Soil loss by water erosion ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
Soil Compaction	Change in topsoil bulk density ($\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)
Soil Sealing	Change in proportion of soil sealing (%/unit)

Some thresholds were then applied to evaluate the intensity of change of each indicator. The mapping approach was a clustering using k-means algorithm. Finally, we described 20 bundles that were grouped for interpretation purposes into 4 groups, from a group where the 4 threats won't be significant in 2050, to a group where 3 threats will be moderate to high (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Bundle of 4 soil threats at the EU level by 2050

Bundles of soil-based ecosystem services

Five soil-based ecosystem services (SES) were considered for the evaluation of the bundles (Table 2), and each of them was evaluated by modelling using available spatial data at the European scale.

Table 2: list of the SES taken into account in the evaluation of the bundles, together with their indicators

SES	Indicator
Primary Biomass Production	Potential net primary production ($\text{gC m}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$)
Soil Erosion control	Soil not eroded by water ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$)
Climate regulation	Net ecosystem productivity ($\text{gC m}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$)
Water production	Water yield (P-ETP) (mm yr^{-1})
Flood control	Soil water storage capacity (mm)

The evaluation of bundles was made by giving a score to each SES – 1 for a low level of SES, 10 for a median level of SES, and 100 for a high level of SES – and then to sum all the scores. It finally gives 7 categories of bundles, from a bundle where all the 5 SES are low (black in figure 13 with a final score equal to 5), to a bundle where all the 5 SES are high (purple in figure 13 with a final score equal to 500).

Figure 13: Bundle of 5 SES at the EU level

4.1.3. Short description of the audience

66 persons registered to the webinar, and about half of them attended it. Representatives from the European Commission, the DG Agri, the JRC attended the meeting, together with some stakeholders in Member states, and EJP SOIL scientists.

In order to receive comprehensive (even few) feedbacks, the scientists, especially the SERENA participants, were asked not to answer the Mentimeter polls.

4.2. Results: the feedback of stakeholders to EU maps of bundles

4.2.1. Evaluation of soil threats bundles

The stakeholders were asked to give their interest and understanding regarding the mapping of soil threats bundles. For most of them, the use of bundles is of interest in their practices (Figure 14-a), and seems to be a good option to explore the complexity of the soil functioning, especially the threats leading to a degradation state (Figure 14-c). The way they have been produced in SERENA is generally understandable (Figure 14-b) and seems to be interesting, because they are not some statistical evaluations, but have been calculated by realistic models.

Figure 14: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the interest of soil threats bundle the EU level

However, even if the maps produced by SERENA are understandable, they do not completely fit their expectations. Some stakeholders would have appreciated an evaluation more focused on actions, instead of “only” a state situation (Figure 14-d).

Regarding the scenarios used, they generally think it is of interest for them (Figure 15-a), but they could have chosen other ones (Figure 15-b); an intermediate IPCC scenario, and not only the 2 extreme ones would have been meaningful. Moreover, a realistic scenario regarding farming practices would have been useful, in order to identify more precisely the remediation actions to be implemented to preserve soils. However, such farming practices were not available and then not implemented in the models.

Figure 15: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the use of scenarios to soil threats bundle at the EU level

An important point regarding the evaluation of bundles is the weighting between them. In the SERENA approach, no choice has been made regarding this weighting, and most of the stakeholders disagree with this approach (Figure 16-a): they would have given more importance to erosion (Figure 16-b). On the other hand, only 4 threats have been evaluated

here, based on a previous prioritisation of SERENA participants at the beginning of the project. A different one may occur today, including especially biodiversity loss, the actual main threat of interest for the stakeholders participating to the webinar.

Figure 16: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the weighting and prioritisation of soil threats bundle the EU level

4.2.2. Evaluation of SES bundles

As for soil threats, the stakeholders were asked to provide feedbacks regarding the mapping of SES. Only a few of them answered the following questions; the results given here are then to be considered with caution.

However, the evaluation of SES is of interest for them (Figure 17-b and 17-c), and the corresponding map is generally understandable (Figure 17-a), even if the added value of calculating bundles is not that evident for some stakeholders.

Figure 17: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the interest of SES bundle the EU level

An important methodological point in evaluation SES bundles is the choice of thresholds, which aims at evaluating if a SES is “high” or “low”. As far as no specific method is available in the literature, the SERENA consortium has developed its own one; it was not completely understood or acknowledged by the stakeholders (results not shown here).

The proposition of giving the same importance to all the SES in the evaluation of their bundle seems comprehensive (Figure 18-a), but erosion control as well as flood regulation appear to be the most important SES for the stakeholders to day (Figure 18-b).

Figure 18: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the weighting and prioritisation of SES bundle the EU level

A last set of questions concerned the evaluation of SES at the 2050 horizon, by using the same scenarios than the ones used for the soil threats evaluation. The few stakeholders answering the part of the poll said that the use of scenarios are of interest, but the comparison between actual bundles and future bundles sometimes appears confusing. It may be due to compensating effects in some models.

4.2.3. Take-home messages and general discussion

A general discussion highlighted that the stakeholders usually agree with the SERENA take-home messages regarding the bundles: they can be evaluated by using a model, say the choice of the indicator is of key importance and the uncertainties have to be taken into account (Figure 19). However, they highlighted that this comprehensive research exercise does not allow to look at the locations where actions have to be done, and neither gives some recommendations regarding these actions. They also warn about the evaluation of an incomplete set of threats or ecosystem services: the location with “no threat” or “high level of SES” may be overinterpreted by users not familiar with the approach.

Figure 19: Stakeholders' feedbacks about the SERENA take-home messages regarding the evaluation and use of bundles

5. Conclusions

The evaluation of the SERENA products was conducted both at the national and EU scales. The evaluation of national maps by some stakeholders highlighted the discrepancy between the recipients as well as with the countries. Farmers usually were not likely to evaluate the regional/national maps, which do not give any relevant information for their local soil management. The bundles still seem to be unfamiliar for most of the stakeholders who have participated to the evaluation activity.

The evaluation of EU maps of bundles demonstrated that the concept of bundles appeared interesting but quite unfamiliar to some stakeholders. An important knowledge gap regarding this approach is the actual lack of weighting between either threats or ecosystem services. However, the approach seems to be meaningful in the context of the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Law. Some next interactions between EJP SOIL scientists and EU stakeholders could be i) to evaluate the possibility of including a bundle approach in the JCR EU dashboard, and ii) to map soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services at the soil district resolution.

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